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MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE TYMUS OF PREMATURE STILLBORN INFANTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14264185>

Abstract: Premature stillborn babies continue to have a violation of the integrated functional connection with the thymus and adrenal glands, which are not yet fully formed, according to the mortality rate, at 22-27, 28-32, 33-38 weeks. Those who died from intrauterine infection in the antenatal period make up 78.2% of all babies and form the basis of our research. As the main morphological substrate of these changes, it was found that the reticuloepithelial cells of the thymus cortex are small in size, the desmosomas are short and thick, there are many sparse fibrous structures connecting the spaces between desmosomas, and the hematohistogenic barrier has become functionally impaired.

Key words: thymus, morphology, involution, immunodeficiency, necrosis,

The relevance of the problem: It is understood that premature birth of the fetus due to intrauterine infection is 1-4% of every 1000 births in the world of newborns or perinatal pathologies. Among the developed countries, in the USA and Europe, this indicator is on average 4-5 per 1000 births. In the world's top five, Turkmenistan has 45, Tajikistan 33, Azerbaijan 21, Kyrgyzstan 17 and Uzbekistan 16 cases per 1000 births. This indicates that full screening of extragenital diseases during fetal development or examinations that should be done during pregnancy have not been fully implemented. In perinatal pathologies, antenatal death mainly develops together with infectious and non-infectious etiological processes and manifests itself in the form of fetal immaturity, asphyxia, birth trauma, pneumopathies, perinatal blood circulation disorders in the brain, and hemorrhagic disease of newborns.

The purpose of the research is to study the pathomorphological characteristics of the thymus tissue during antenatal death of infants.

Material and methods: morphological methods of thymus tissue of stillborn babies in the antenatal period were used.

Result and discussion: Compared with this period in the norm, taking into account that the wall of the thymus lobes has a flat trajectory, in the studied group, there is a sharp thickening of the sparse fibrous connective tissue in the wall of the lobes, the formation of septa with a rough appearance, macrophages in large numbers in the perivascular areas, 7-12 in the cytoplasm with a size of 200x undergoing apoptosis meeting of lymphocytes, triangular and star-like appearance of reticulo-epithelial cells, becoming long-fibrous, empty bare areas in between, means a sharp decrease in lymphocytes. It was found that in most of the fragments there was a collapse, a large number of lymphocytes around macrophages, a large number of phagocytosis foci, and a sharp decrease in thymic hormone-producing cells. These changes indicate that the thymus undergoes accidental transformation over time, at different stages in the process. In the postcapillary venules of the cortex, there is a sharp fullness, sedimentation of erythrocytes, swellings in the perivascular areas, reticuloepithelial cells have a short thickened appearance, and dystrophic changes. Focal accumulation of nanny cells, bare areas around them, small lymphoblasts were found. Morphological changes in the cells characteristic of all the intramural tissues of the sebaceous glands mean that the number of lymphocytes that make up the thymus parenchyma at the expense of the fibrous structures is reduced, macrophages are split between the plasmatic fibrous structures, the process of induced apoptosis is increased, and the morphofunctional areas are sharply reduced. A small number of dendritic cells means that hematogenous T lymphocytes do not fully recognize histological antigens and the rate of apoptosis is increased.

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